

Multipolar Mediation: China's Expanding Security Role in the Saudi-Iran Rivalry

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Abstract

This article examined how China has developed its role in the security arena of the Persian Gulf in terms of historical trends in the enemy relationship between Saudi Arabia and Iran. It has pursued an interventionist approach as far as foreign policy goes. However, China's significant role in bringing about the Saudi-Iran Detente indicated a clear shift toward diplomatic assertiveness. This article provides an overview of China's engagement in terms of security, such as arms sales, technology transfers, and multilateral coordination through organizations like the Shanghai Cooperation Organization (SCO), and more general balancing between rival Gulf powers. Data sources for qualitative analysis include official documents related to diplomacy, trade agreements, and security cooperation, which create a picture of how China manages to sustain influence without direct military involvement. Although China remained economically and politically neutral on regional conflicts, it projected itself as a stabilizing power and was lightly contesting traditional Western security actors in the region. The article concludes that while China's mediation model is conflict-averse, it offers a viable alternative to multipolar diplomacy and has ramifications for Gulf security architecture.

Introduction

The Persian Gulf remains a focal point for any discussion of the global security architecture. It is a region rife with sectarian divisions, historical rivalries, and ever-present geopolitical contests, and it has frequently become a theatre for both direct and proxy confrontations. Instability finds its roots in the moot finding that antagonism between Saudi Arabia and Iran, two regional powers having clashing ideological orientations, security priorities, and international alliances has fostered the political and military dynamics of Yemen and Syria, Iraq and Lebanon (Mabon, 2013). Thus, the tension generated by this enmity has translated into mistrust and periods of escalation. To moderate and occasionally stabilize this volatile environment, extra-regional actors, particularly the United States, have historically engaged in an inconsistent pattern of security guarantees, selling arms, and deploying their military presence in significant numbers within the Gulf.

In light of the above, China's agenda in the Persian Gulf has recently been mainly economic involvement and caution on the diplomatic scene. On the principle of non-interference, China has hesitated to become involved in the complex security issues of the region. Energy security, economic

partnerships, and state sovereignty figured much higher in the scale of all national interests in the foreign policy calculus of China than strategic or military projection. But as the economic footprint of Beijing grew especially through oil-for-infrastructure deals, the Belt and Road Initiative, and trade in yuan as an essential strategic change began to creep into view. China's mediation of the rapprochement between Iran and Saudi Arabia in March 2023 has been one of the strongest indicators of this shift. Thus, the Beijing deal represented the first public acknowledgment by China to take third-party security mediation responsibilities for an area long influenced by Western powers (Zhang, Ashwarya, & Wen, 2023). Though the accord did not address the more profound structural rift between the two states, it did signify, if only symbolically, Beijing's potential as a diplomatic alternative in a multipolar world. Thus, China's participation in the mediation epitomizes growing confidence and reinforces the country's interest in achieving stability in the region as a prerequisite for uninterrupted energy flow and successful long-term strategic investments.

Indeed, there was a lot of work done regarding its economic diplomacy. Still, not much has been talked about the emerging

security role that China will play, especially concerning its diplomatic, military-technical, and multilateral dealings in the region. This understanding can only come from seeing how China nurtures concurrent relations with rival powers, uses arms diplomacy and strategic neutrality, and exploits multilateral institutions such as the Shanghai Cooperation Organization in this regard. The article analyzes the security posture that China has been developing in the Persian Gulf, concentrating on strategic balancing with Saudi Arabia and Iran. The article examines how China balances its non-military measures i.e, mediation, arms transfer, and regional forums making itself credible as a security stakeholder without overt military commitment. The research is based on qualitative content analysis of agreements signed in diplomatic circles, documents related to defense cooperation, and regional policy discourses to offer a comprehensive view of the changing position of China in Gulf security and its implications in regional power shifts and global strategic realignments.

Purpose of Study

This research examines how China is changing its role in the Persian Gulf security architecture, particularly against the background of Saudi-Iran rivalry. Historically

espousing a non-interventionist policy, China has now modified its stance to include diplomatic arbitration, arms diplomacy, and regional engagement through platforms such as the Shanghai Cooperation Organization (SCO). Hence, this article examines how China continues to diffuse security influence without direct military power and how such a behavioral proclivity fits into a broader shift toward multipolar diplomacy in the Middle East.

Research Methodology

A qualitative research methodology was adopted whereby content analysis was employed as the primary tool to unpack official diplomatic documents, arms transfer agreements, multilateral platform activities, and pertinent secondary academic literature. Key data sources highlight statements from the Chinese Ministry of Foreign Affairs, Saudi-Iranian defense cooperation reports, policy papers from international think tanks, and scholarly evaluations of China's role in its Gulf security architecture. The study juxtaposes this material to highlight key themes and patterns in China's security posture.

China's Mediation in the Saudi-Iran Rivalry

A. Diplomatic Mediation

China has shifted from a strategy of avoiding regional conflicts to actively mediating in the

Middle East, most notably between Saudi Arabia and Iran. In March 2023, China brokered a landmark agreement in Beijing, which facilitated the reopening of diplomatic channels between the two rival nations. (Xinchun & Shaoxian, 2023) . This agreement followed years of hostility, including severed ties in 2016 after the Saudi execution of a prominent Shia cleric and the storming of Saudi missions in Iran. China's success as a mediator can be attributed to its impartiality. Unlike the United States, which is frequently viewed as a partisan actor in the region, China is not aligned with any ideological or political faction. Emphasizing economic stability instead of military intervention has allowed a credible and impartial negotiator to emerge. This change can be viewed as a sign of China's growing confidence in tackling some of the world's diplomatic problems; however, along with this comes a host of questions about the long-term effects of its involvement in Middle Eastern affairs. However, such could trigger a basic change in the dynamics of international relations.

The strife between Saudi Arabia and Iran has widened on various fronts, with a wide range of issues, such as sectarian rivalries between Sunni and Shia, increasingly bosom proxy wars in Yemen and Syria, and mutual

accusations of sabotage. Mediation from this corner appeared to reflect an interest in making regional stability work for China's economic and strategic interests, such as oil imports and initiatives under the BRI (BRI).

Key Essentials for Successful Mediation in China

Balanced Relations

The secret of the Chinese model for success is characterised by strong but equal relationships between Saudi Arabia and Iran, which run counter to the typical US approach construed as going too far in the way of Saudi Arabia.

Saudi Arabia

Saudi Arabia provides major oil to China, which is essential for Beijing's energy security. China is stepping up its collaboration with Saudi Arabia so that it can take the seat of a negotiator next in the region. The renewed partnerships are in place to make significant investments and sign contracts in sync with Saudi Arabia's Vision 2030, especially on initiatives in renewable energy (Foley, 2023). With these efforts, China can thus realize its support for the kingdom's sustainable development as well as economic diversification goals. Together, these would localize, transfer, and apply technology to reduce oil dependence. Furthermore, amid this is the State-backed inclusion of Saudi

Arabia into the global economy because the former is enthusiastic about the BRI by China. The partnership between the two countries' Vision 2030 and One Belt One Road Initiative represents a strategic collaboration aimed at redefining regional dynamics while building increased bilateral relations for more future partnerships that would influence the global political and economic landscape. Both countries have also enhanced their partnership through infrastructure and renewable energy projects aligned with Saudi Vision 2030.

Iran

This is evident by the partnership's trajectory: US sanctions notwithstanding, China has been a significant economic partner for Iran and signed a 25-year strategic cooperation agreement in 2021 (Taneja, et al., 2023). It included Chinese investments in Iranian infrastructure, oil trade neutrality, and non-evident billions of dollars via billions a week. In contrast to Western nations, China adopts the policy of non-intervention in foreign countries' internal affairs. This neutrality, thus, made Beijing an unbiased candidate for any mediation that did not attach itself to biasedness. Therefore, the Chinese approach emphasizes dialogue and mutual respect instead of coercion or conditionality-based approaches, leaving

space for trust between two conflicting parties.

This agreement has brought down many tensions in many conflict-ridden areas, such as Yemen, where the two countries were backing very different factions in the conflict. The mediation offered by China enabled both parties to become more amenable and thus possibly prepared for future peace talks regarding the regions, as mentioned earlier. Chinese mediation of the Saudi-Iran rapprochement helped stabilize the Gulf, for which stability inter alia is vital for energy exports, maritime security, and regional economic cooperation, besides being advantageous to China and global markets. In short, China's successful mediation will boost its status as a global power capable of resolving conflicts through diplomacy instead of military intervention. This has wider ramifications for its ambitions to reshape the global order and promote a multipolar world.

B. Correlation Between China's Interests in the Persian Gulf and Its Influence on Saudi-Iran Relations

Strategic motives for China's engagement with the Persian Gulf mainly revolve around the country's energy security interests, economic aspirations, and geopolitical objectives. As a sign of its dependency on the energy supplies of Saudi Arabia and Iran, the

largest oil-importing country in the world is required to conduct a careful, balanced approach to foreign affairs, not to jeopardize the flow of energy resources. On the other hand, China's policies concerning Saudi-Iran relations are determined by its interests in the Gulf and thus require Beijing to make a balanced, pragmatic, and economic-first approach. For example, energy security and stability in the Gulf are critical for China, with Saudi Arabia continually being China's top oil supplier. Likewise, the country's energy security concerns also shape much of its diplomacy in de-escalating tensions between Riyadh and Tehran. China's BRI (BRI), one of China's significant factors compelling this policy in the Gulf, sees Saudi Arabia and Iran as strategic partners in Beijing's BRI. Thus, the Chinese are not taking sides in the Saudi-Iran competition but are promoting economic engagement with both countries to pursue their economic goals.

1. Mediation as a Power Play: China's Role in Conflict Resolution

The long-term ambitions that China has attached to itself in the realm of global geopolitics and then engagement in competition with Western powers, primarily the United States, also alter the posture of the People's Republic of China in the

Persian Gulf. China brokered the Saudi-Iran peace deal in 2023; this was another time the country used to further build a partnership with any country through the economic door toward regional diplomacy, thereby intensifying China's role in the Persian Gulf's affairs (Cafiero, 2023). In reality, however, China's careful approach has proved unsuccessful in navigating the delicate diplomacy needed to strike a balance between Saudi Arabia and Iran: Saudi Arabia is complicated by being a US ally and thereby not easily integrated with Gulf security arrangements while miscalculating the unpredictable nature of foreign policy by Iran and the effect of Western sanctions; both of these pose dangers to Chinese investments. In addition, regional conflicts like the Yemen war require China to disentangle itself from this complicated web of alliances and rivalries. The growing influence of Beijing in Saudi-Iran relations is part of its long-term strategic goals in the Gulf, which are to stretch from energy security and economic growth to geopolitical balancing and eliminate Western influences. These diplomatic and economic ties with Iran and Saudi Arabia ensure stabilization, protection, and reduction of price volatility along energy supply chains. The BRI aligns with China's Gulf strategy in that Saudi

Arabia is at the centre of its infrastructure investments. Iran is the other important partner linking the Middle East with China's land-based trade routes. China has sought the mediation process to ratchet up the pressure against the US's hegemony over the region.

2. China's Calculated Risk: Engaging Iran Without Provoking Saudi Arabia

Another reason for this was to lessen the US dependency on the energy markets and financial systems under its control and weaken Washington's economic leverage, for instance, concerning sanctions on Iran. However, China has continued to import Iranian oil, thus keeping Iran's economy afloat while extracting fat revenues from Saudi Arabia. China prefers to reduce conflicts between Saudi Arabia and Iran for the long-term security and economic interests in the Gulf. By doing this, Beijing hopes to contain violence in its diplomatic initiatives and ensure that investments are secure and profitable. With this, China also kept itself away from direct military commitments in the region and thus enhanced its standing as a neutral power broker. Increased Chinese influence in the Persian Gulf region poses several strategic challenges concerning growing bilateral relations between China, Saudi Arabia and Iran. China strikes a

delicate balance here, straddling the act of gaining economic and geopolitical advantages from rival countries. In contrast, other factors, such as regional rivalries, security concerns, and external pressures, come into play.

Arms Sales and Military Cooperation

China has made considerable inroads into the 21st century as an influential contributor to regional security order in the Gulf, as a manifestation of balancing its relationship with Saudi Arabia and Iran and its geopolitical and economic interests. Historically, China has followed a non-interference policy with a prime emphasis on economic cooperation. However, in the past few years, the developments in military cooperation, arms exports, and strategic security engagement have allowed the Chinese to present itself as an essential entity in the security dynamics of the Persian Gulf. Chinese security involvement revolves around significant arms sales and military cooperation programs with Saudi Arabia and Iran. With the technology transfer for missile systems to Saudi Arabia, cooperation in joint exercises, and technology support with the Riyadh defence industry, China allows Saudi Arabia to diversify military procurement away from Western arms. Chinese defence ties with Iran have also significantly ratified

the strategic cooperation agreement for 25 years (Fan & Najafabad, 2024). What it would do over the years is supply missile systems, drone technology, and nautical equipment to bolster Iranian defensive capabilities, especially under the pressures of Western sanctions. In this context, Iran has also conducted joint military exercises with China and Russia, thus adopting an alternative security perception beyond US-led alliances.

Beyond direct military cooperation, China is also using multilateral platforms like the Shanghai Cooperation Organization to extend its outreach further in the region. In 2023, SCO has now welcomed Iran as a full-fledged member of its roster; it is a security coordination forum where China can participate in counterterrorism, intelligence-sharing and regional security collaboration (Sun, 2024). However, for all that, the SCO does not function as a military alliance like NATO, and its spread shows China's intent to assume a far more assertive role in regional security affairs. China remains chiefly a diplomatic player in terms of engagement in regional security and conflict affairs, as opposed to an active military one. This contrasts with the case of US-based sprawling military bases across the Gulf. On the contrary, China's behaviour is very much

neutral and mediatory during regional conflict. We could see this from the recent reconciliation between Iran and Saudi Arabia, where China facilitated conversing between the two parties while paving the way for reduced sectarian and geopolitical tensions.

Thus, China will progressively assert itself by gaining access to strategic energy resources in its stabilizing interventionist force. In other words, China's multilayered security strategy inside the Gulf encompasses arms sales, military cooperation, intelligence sharing, and diplomatic mediation. It is causative by generally determining external conditions for developing countries. They also favor giving regions of developing countries a preference for defence import contracts when awarded to a military defence contractor. In this way, China secures its interests in energy while countering US predominance in the region as it pursues ever-deeper relations with Saudi Arabia and Iran. With this enhanced influence, China understands that it must balance the competing regional rivals against each other and thus improve its security posture, which is a key agent of change in the Gulf dynamics.

The Balancing Act Between Saudi & Iran

Saudi Arabia and Iran have been engaged in historical rivalries for years, which have

transformed into proxy conflicts. Both countries want China to mediate for peace, while both are also vying for regional hegemony, making it harder for Beijing to remain non-aligned. Saudi Arabia is an ally of the US and is at the forefront of the GCC, and complementary Western security settings are of interest to it. Whereas Iran has been largely under US sanctions, Western collaboration with China would have been naturally an economic opportunity for Iran to turn toward China for help. Analysis suggests that China would risk its goodwill with Saudi Arabia and the wider GCC, especially toward potential Western security cooperation, if it further consolidated relations with Iran. Beijing now faces the dilemma of whether to increase intervention or to stick to its current policy of non-intervention, which would, in turn, hurt its geopolitical influence. This will make relations infinitely more complicated, as sanctions and economic interdependence constitute a problem that is mostly in conflict because while Saudi Arabia remains China's largest oil supplier, Iran is one of China's top partners in the BRI. External powers are still critical to shaping the geopolitical realities in the Middle East, as the US and Russia. Hence, China must negotiate with the two nations in the context

of security dilemmas, economic risks, and geopolitical rivalries while being careful not to become too estranged from either nation.

Key Findings

- In the Gulf, China has a non-military strategy for security that is based on diplomatic mediation, economic interdependence, and involvement in soft security issues while avoiding troop deployments and military alliances.
- By brokering the Saudi-Iran normalization deal in 2023, China created a watershed moment in its own regional role as a neutral mediator in a traditionally U.S.-dominated environment for security itself.
- Through arms diplomacy and technology transfers of drones and missile systems to both Saudi Arabia and Iran, China is creating strategic trust and promoting diversification of regional states' defence ties away from the West.
- Multilateral forums like the Shanghai Cooperation Organization (SCO) are essential for China, where it can extend the regional assurances of legitimacy and coordinating mechanisms without any formal security commitments.
- It has balanced conducting a dual engagement strategy by maintaining closer relations with rival Saudi Arabia and Iran

without letting itself be seen in any other image other than being politically neutral.

- Such a role leads to a multipolar order of the Persian Gulf in the absence of the United States, wherein influence becomes increasingly indirect, exercised through economic leverage and strategic balance instead of direct force.
- Gulf security engagement of China marks a new statecraft-to-trade, diplomatic neutrality, and institutional presence that might now overturn traditional concepts of regional influence.

Conclusion and Recommendations

China's increased involvement in the security setting of the Gulf reflects a strategic orientation away from its stated non-interventionist policy. China does not pursue binding military pacts or permanent base establishments. Still, it describes itself instead as a diplomatic stabilizer and strategic balancer in one of the most dangerous regions in the world.

Third-party mediation offers China an avenue through which to influence competing regional actors without compromising relations with either. The 2023 Saudi-Iran rapprochement resolve came to be considered as a prime instance of Chinese mediation, while arms diplomacy remains the other front categorically

considered by China to try to win influence without taking sides. Using multilateral frameworks such as the Shanghai Cooperation Organization (SCO), China maintains high visibility as a soft-security actor, lending itself legitimacy and leadership, while ensuring its presence without conventional military options.

This mode of engagement emphasizes the broader transition to multipolar security dynamics, where non-Western powers will exert influence via economic leverage, diplomatic credibility, and institutional cooperation. China's engagement in the Gulf is a case study for how great powers can choose to influence regional order without risking coercive means.

Recommendations

- **Encourage the Establishment of Conflict Mediation Platforms:** To earn credibility and continue its peacebuilding efforts into the future, China must turn its mediation role into an institutionalized one through regional diplomacy frameworks located in the Gulf or the "China-GCC Dialogue Forums".
- **Balance Arms Diplomacy with De-escalation Mechanisms:** China should balance arms sales to the region with Joint Confidence Building Measures (JCBM) training protocols, transparency measures, or

restricted use provisions designed to prevent an arms race.

- **Expand Multilateral Security Engagement:** It should deepen involvement in the region through possible enlargement of the SCO or through cooperative security frameworks that bring Gulf actors into counterterrorism, piracy, and maritime security.
- **Avoid Overcommitment in Rivalries:** To keep itself in the frame as a credible broker, China needs to remain neutral, especially in renewed conflict, and avoid siding heavily with either Saudi Arabia or Iran.
- **Leverage Economic Tools for Stability:** Continue to utilize infrastructure, energy partnerships, and digital investment to secure long-term regional stability and reduce prospects for conflict from an economic perspective.

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